

AN INDIVIDUAL APPROACH TO LEARNING DICTATED BY THE TIMES**Polumeeva I.***Senior lecturer at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10514769>***Abstract**

The article by Polumeeva I.N. considers the issue of the relevance of an individual approach, the benefits of feedback for the teacher, indicates the need for feedback to understand the perception and expectations of the audience and draws attention to understanding of the individual approach by students.

Аннотация

В статье Полумеевой И.Н. рассмотрен вопрос актуальности индивидуального подхода, пользы для преподавателя обратной связи, указана необходимость проведения обратной связи для понимания восприятия и ожиданий аудитории слушателей и обращается внимание на понимание обучаемыми индивидуального подхода.

Keywords: individual approach, individual characteristics, feedback, personification of learning, personal contact.

Ключевые слова: индивидуальный подход, индивидуальные особенности, обратная связь, персонификация обучения, личный контакт.

Modern conditions of society's development pose many tasks to specialists of different professions, the solution of which requires knowledge and skills in using computer programs, innovative methods and technologies, readiness and ability to learn, and the desire to keep up with the times. The teaching profession is no exception, school teachers, teachers of higher educational institutions, responding to the challenges of modernity, work with students both offline and online, practice mixed learning. Teachers not only organize and conduct educational and methodological work and carry out curricula, in accordance with the educational programs but also participate in research activities. These are not all the responsibilities of a modern teacher. Many specialists can be involved in the organization of the learning process, but their work is aimed at its main participants, the teacher and the student. Learning is a two-way process carried out by the teacher and the student. The pedagogical dictionary defines learning as an organized, controlled process of interaction between teachers and students aimed at acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, forming a worldview, developing the mental and potential capabilities of students, developing and consolidating self-education skills in accordance with the defined goals. [1, 61]

The assimilation of knowledge and the development of opportunities, as well as self-education skills, are not the same for all students, the learning process takes place at different rates depending on the individual capabilities of students, their previous educational experience, preferences in learning technologies, psychological characteristics and this requires an individual approach to learning. In pedagogical theory, an individual approach is considered as one of the most important principles of learning. An individual approach is an important psychological and pedagogical principle. Pedagogical impact is always mediated by the psy-

chological characteristics of the person who it is directed to and the effectiveness of the impact is determined by how this impact is perceived by a person. [2, 177] The individual psychological characteristics of the student should be taken into account when choosing teaching methods and techniques, teaching methods should vary taking into account the individual characteristics of the student, try to find the optimal combination of frontal, group and individual forms of training. [3]

The technical capabilities that the teacher uses today make it possible to get feedback from students in a few minutes. Thus, the educational portal of our university allows you to upload questions for conducting a survey to the platform in the appropriate course of students and see the opinion or achievements of a group of students. If you need to personally contact or give an individual assignment to the listener, you can send a message or assignment personally to the student. Such a personalized approach allows the teacher to maintain contact with the student, answer questions about the content and organization of the course, especially for first-year students. And the listeners, in turn, see in the individually oriented approach the attention and support of the teacher, the opportunity to ask questions not in front of the entire audience, but individually and in writing. The personality-oriented learning process allows you to constantly monitor current changes in students, the formation of competencies and personal development, which is based on the desire for self-actualization and self-development. [4, 127]

The first- and second-year students were asked to take a survey on the topic of individual assignments. Being asked if individual tasks are needed, when you do not understand the topic, 46% answered in the affirmative, 35% - in the negative and 19% chose the option - I find it difficult to answer. Figure 1 shows the percentage of all responses.

Figure1 Individual tasks

To the question of what individual tasks are needed for, the answer was repeated in different versions – to understand a complex topic, as well as to consolidate new material, find out the weaknesses of the student, increase knowledge, to popularize the subject, to solve particular problems, to gain additional points, in order for the student to find out what topics need to

be addressed pay attention and work through them. In Figure 2, you can see the percentage of the choice of the form of completing the task, 47% chose electronically, 35% in writing and 18% orally. The main part preferred to work in electronic form, which was expected.

Figure 2 The form of individual tasks.

Questions were also asked about the consultancy. When asked whether teachers should have consultation hours, 61% of respondents believe that they should, 23% answered negatively and 16% found it difficult to answer. Moreover, many of those who answered negatively gave a detailed answer, where they noted that the workload of teachers does not allow, in their opinion, to conduct full-fledged consultancy. What consultancy is needed for, 85% believe in order to ask questions on the topic, 15% in order to get additional tasks.

Conclusion

At this stage of education development, the issues of an individual approach to teaching and individualization of learning are perceived by teachers and students as a fact, as an actual reality. The tasks assigned to a modern teacher include not only conducting classes and evaluating students, developing programs and directing the scientific activities of students, but also teaching analysis, critical thinking, self-organization and self-development.

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